

There was a whole country who swallowed a lie

There was a whole country who swallowed a lie
I don't know why they swallowed a lie – perhaps they'll die!

There was a whole country that burned lots of coal,
That polluted and polluted the world as whole;
They burned the coal because they swallowed a lie;
I don't know why they swallowed a lie – Perhaps they'll die!

There was a whole sunny country that imported fossil fuel oil,
How absurd to import fossil fuel oil;
They imported fossil oil and they burned lots of coal;
They burned and combusted because that's what they were told;
I don't know why they swallowed the lie – Perhaps they'll die!

There was a whole country that ignited their gas,
Fancy that to ignite toxic gas;
That emits methane and carbon dioxide causing ecological collapse;
They ignited their gas to distract from importing fossil oil;
They imported fossil oil and they burned lots of coal;
They burned, combusted and ignited them all because of the lie;
I don't know why they swallowed the lie – Perhaps they'll die!

There was a whole country tricked into nuclear power,
What a greedy unsustainable abuse of power;
Nuclear is dangerous and more expensive than wind and solar power;
They were tricked into nuclear to keep moguls in ivory towers;
They ignited their gas to distract from importing fossil fuel oil;
They imported fossil fuel oil and they burned lots of coal;
They burned, combusted and ignited them all because of the lie;
I don't know why they swallowed the lie – Perhaps they'll die!

There was a whole country who failed to take a clean energy renewable course...
They're dead, of course!